

MIT ART, DESIGN AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY
MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

7th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
RECENT TRENDS IN BIOENGINEERING
(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

MIT School of
**Bioengineering Sciences
& Research**

Breathe Life into Engineering Career!

**MIT-ADT
UNIVERSITY**
PUNE, INDIA

A Leap Towards The World Class Education

OP-027

Engineering the Tumor Microenvironment: A novel strategy in Breast Cancer therapeutics

Manpreet Kaur^{1*}, Kashish Arora¹, Rajiv Kumar Devgan², Jatinder Singh³

¹Department of Human Genetics, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, Punjab, India

²Department of Radiation Oncology, GND Hospital Government Medical College, Amritsar, Punjab, India

³Department of Molecular Biology and Biochemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, Punjab, India

*Corresponding: dr.manpreetdhunna@gmail.com

Abstract: Breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer and is leading cause of cancer related deaths among women worldwide. Increasing incidence and mortality for breast cancer, in spite of availability of various therapies, is a matter of deep concern. In the last few years, sufficient data has emerged to advocate role of various non-cancerous cells (stromal cells), present in the vicinity of cancer cells, in modulating proliferating/invasive properties of cancer cells. Proliferating tumor cells along with these non-cancerous cells comprises Tumor microenvironment (TME). Besides stromal cells, major immune cells infiltrate into TME and are linked to poor prognosis of breast cancer. Various molecules are secreted in the TME that impact proliferation, apoptotic behaviour, angiogenic ability of cancer cell, along with extra-cellular matrix remodeling. A significant cell population in breast TME is known to be tumor-associated macrophages (TAM), which is characterised by M2 phenotype, associated with pro-tumorigenic properties. TAMs are known to express various pro-angiogenic growth factors, cytokines, and chemokines and macrophage colony stimulating factor. Annexins, another class of molecules, have significant role in modulating TME and thus the disease state. Secretome studies have reported the presence of annexins A1-A6 in the secretome of the breast TME and their critical importance. In light of the above studies, it is plausible that the components of TME can be crucial targets in defining invasive, anti-apoptotic and migratory behaviour of cancer cells. Targeting these molecules will be of great benefit for effective management of the disease.

Keywords: Annexins, cancer, macrophage polarization, tumor-associated macrophages, tumor microenvironment.

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

Bioengineering is a multidisciplinary field that has gained immense importance in the global scenario. MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research is a constituent unit of MIT Art, Design and Technology University that aims to prepare students for ambitious careers in bioengineering by imparting education and hands-on training through project-based learning. The school helps in introducing students to the world of untapped opportunities in biology using engineering skills. The school envisions to empower India to become a leader in Bioengineering research, development and manufacturing sectors. It offers B. Tech. (Bioengineering), Int. M. Tech. (Bioengineering), M. Tech. (Environmental Bioengineering), M.Sc (Industrial Biotechnology) and Ph.D Programs in Biotechnology, Biomedical Engineering, Bioinformatics and Biomaterials. The super-specialized courses include Pharmaceutical Engineering, Synthetic Biology, Big Data Analytics, Biosensors and IoT, Biomedical Imaging, Biomechanics, Nano-Biotechnology, Robotics, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, Environmental bioengineering, etc. The school is equipped with state-of-art laboratories for carrying out high-end research and innovative product development.

Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

9 789360 390518